

STUDY ON RECYCLING CARBON FIBRE THERMOPLASTIC PREPREG WASTE

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ABSTRACT

In order to reduce the environmental burden by the weight saving of vehicles, fibre reinforced plastics have been used as metal substitutes. The application of CF RTP (carbon fibre reinforced thermoplastics) is expected because of its high mechanical property together with process ability. However, there are unavoidable wastes when CF RTP prepreg sheets are cut into specific geometries to charge moulds with them. Therefore, it is necessary to utilize the CF RTP wastes by a recycling system from both the environmental and economical point of view. Recently, hybrid injection moulding that combines the press moulding and insert injection moulding has attracted attentions. The hybrid injection moulding system is as follow. After heated insert material is pre-formed by pressmoulding, the pre-formed insert material is overmoulded by injection moulding machine. These processes are carried out in the one cycle. In this paper, we propose the recycling method of prepreg wastes and characterize the recycled material. Furthermore, we investigated the potency of the recycled material for the hybrid injection moulding. We carried out numerical analysis to examine the interfacial characteristics. Our recycled material is prepared as pellets by neading, the wastes of prepreg in twin-screw extruder with neat polymer. The fuzzless pellets with good fibre dispersion were obtained in low volume fraction of carbon fibres. In spite of the absence of longer fibres, they showed excellent mechanical performance in comparison with conventional materials designing the preferable process conditions. This mechanical advantage would be due to the fact that the recycled pellets were made from the prepreg sheet which had good interfacial adhesion strength. In contrast, the localization of fibres was observed in high volume fraction of fibres and the mechanical property did not improved. This recycled material has a beneficial effort on the hybrid injection moulding. They also achieved excellent interfacial adhesiveness for the hybrid injection moulding between the injected material and the inserted material. It was found that the cost effective recycle pellets which had excellent mechanical performance could be produced optimizing both the fibre volume fraction and process condition in this recycling system.

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the environmental problem such as, global warming caused by increase of carbon-dioxide are getting serious. Reduction of carbon-dioxide emissions and improvement of energy efficiency are an issue all over the world. In order to reduce the environmental burden by the weight saving of vehicles, fibre reinforced plastics have been used as metal substitutes [1] [2]. The application of CF RTP (carbon fibre reinforced thermoplastics) is expected because of its high mechanical property together with process ability. As one method of forming the CF RTP, prepreg were consolidated by heat welding after the prepreg laminate comprising carbon fibre and resin were cut. There are unavoidable wastes when CF RTP prepreg sheets are cut into specific geometries to charge moulds with them. Generated ash by burning the wastes was landfilled because there is no use value. There is an urgent need the establishment of recycle method of scraps with increasing demand of the prepreg. In this study, scraps were pelletized with twin-screw extruder and we examined the recycling method.

Hybrid injection moulding that combines the press moulding and insert injection moulding have attracted attention. The hybrid injection moulding system is as follow. After heated insert material is pre-formed by pressmoulding, the pre-formed insert material is overmoulded by injection moulding machine. These processes are carried out in the one cycle. The recycled pellets are expected as injection materials of hybrid injection moulding that used the recycled pellets to the injection material and used the prepreg to the insert material because the material of the recycled pellets and the prepreg was identity. We proposed the recycling method of prepreg wastes and revealed the characteristic of the recycled pellets. We compared the recycled pellets with the conventional carbon fibre reinforced pellets by injection moulding. Furthermore, we investigated the potency of the recycled material for the hybrid injection moulding. We carried out numerical analysis to examine the interfacial characteristics.

2 EXPERIMENTAL AND RESULTS

2.1 Screw configuration of the twin-screw extruder

2.1.1 Experimental method

Prepreg wastes comprised polypropylene and carbon fibre was used (Mitsubishi Rayon Co., Ltd., Vf31%). The prepreg wastes were kneaded by the twin-screw extruder and pelletized. The screw configurations used in this experiment are shown in Fig 1. Screw 1 was consisted of full flight and kneading and mixing. Screw 2 was consisted of only full flight. We made pellets with each screw configurations. Kneading distance of the screw 1 is 720 mm and kneading distance of the screw2 is 200 mm. The twin-screw extruder condition is shown in Table 1. Fibres were taken out by dissolving the resin of the pellets. The fibres were photographed using a Universal zoom microscope (Nikon Co., Ltd., AZ100). We measured the length of 1000 fibres using an image processing program. The weight mean fibre length L_w was calculated by Eq. (1) where L is measured single fibre length.

$$L_w = \frac{\sum L^2}{\sum L} \quad (1)$$

Figure 1: Screw configurations of twin-screw extruder

Screw speed	[rpm]	120
Temperature	[°C]	200
Shift diameter	[mm]	φ18
L/D (screw 1)	-	40
L/D (screw 2)	-	11

Table 1: The twin-screw extruder condition

2.1.2 Results and discussions

The result of the fibres length measurement is shown in Fig 2. Fibre length of the pellets made with the screw 2 was longer than fibre length of the pellets made with the screw 1. Fibre breakage was

suppressed because shear strength of the screw 2 was lower than shear strength of the screw 1. Two groups of pellets aptly looked alike and both of those were suitable for injection moulding.

Figure 2: Fibres length of the pellets made respective by screw 1 and screw 2

2.2 Evaluations of recycled pellets

2.2.1 Experimental method

We evaluated the characteristics of recycled pellets. The same chapter 2.1 as prepreg wastes were used. We compared the recycled pellets with the conventional carbon fibre reinforced pellets with injection moulding. Short fibre pellets (SFP) and long fibre pellets (LFP) were used as the conventional carbon fibre reinforced pellets. The SFP of fibre content of 17%, 11%, 5% were used (Mitsubishi Rayon Co., Ltd., PYROFIL). The LFP of fibre content of 15%, 11%, 5% were used (Mitsubishi Rayon Co., Ltd.). We referred to the results of chapter 2.1. The prepreg wastes were put through vent port of the twin-screw extruder and the kneading distance was 200 mm. Screw used in the experiment was consisted of only full flight. The fibre content was controlled by putting the polypropylene from the feeder of the twin-screw extruder. The pellets of Vf5%, Vf12%, Vf18%, Vf25%, Vf31% were produced. The fibre content was calculated from Eq. (2). The pellets were dried by an oven dryer (EPPH-212S). The dry condition was at 80°C by 1 day. The moulds were made from the recycled pellets by injection moulding machine (TOYO MACHINERY & METAL CO., LTD., Ltd., PLASTR ET-40V). The twin-screw extruder condition is shown in Table 2 and the injection moulding condition is shown in Table 3. As mechanical property evaluation, tensile strength test, three-point bending test and impact test were conducted. Weight mean fibre length measurement and spiral flow test were conducted. Tensile fracture surface of mouldings were observed by a scanning electron microscope (SEM). The moulds were evaluated in a tensile strength test and three-point bending test using the universal testing machine (Shimadzu Autograph AG-1). In spiral flow test, injection condition was constant because the flow length was affected by the injection pressure, resin temperature and mould temperature. We were compared with the recycled pellets and the conventional pellets in each evaluation.

$$Vf_1 = \frac{Wf_1 \times \rho_m}{\rho_f(1 - Wf_1) + \rho_m \times Wf_1} \quad (2)$$

$$Wf_1 = \frac{A}{A+B} \times \frac{Vf_0 \times \rho_f}{\rho_m(1 - Vf_0) + \rho_f \times Vf_0}$$

Vf_1 : fibre content of the diluted material

Wf_1 : fibre mass content of the diluted material

Vf_0 : fibre content of the raw material

ρ_f : the density of the fibre ρ_m : the density of the matrix

A : prepreg input B : neat resin input

Screw speed	[rpm]	120
Temperature	[°C]	200
L/D	-	40

Table 2: The twin-screw extruder condition

Screw speed	[rpm]	100
Injection pressure	[MPa]	150
Back pressure	[MPa]	2.7
Holding pressure	[MPa]	25
Cylinder temperature	[°C]	200
Mold temperature	[°C]	80
Injection speed	[mm/sec]	50
Hold time	[sec]	12
Cool down time	[sec]	12

Table 3: Injection moulding condition

2.2.2 Results and discussions

Fibre length compared among various fibre content of the recycled pellets and mouldings.

The result of the fibre length measurement of the recycled pellets and mouldings is shown in Fig 3. Fibre length of fibre content of Vf25% and Vf31% was longer than fibre length of other fibre content. The shapes of the recycled pellets as shown in Fig 4 were large in high fibre content. The result of fibre length of the moulding showed that fibre length was shorted in high fibre content compared with the low fibre content because the metering time in injection process of high fibre content was longer than the metering time in injection process of low fibre content.

Figure 3: Fibre length of the recycled pellets and the moludings

Figure 4: The shapes of the recycle pellets of various fibre content

Mechanical property of various fibre content of the recycled pellets moldings

Fig 5, 6, 7 showed tensile property, flexural property and impact strength of the recycled pellets respectively. Tensile modulus and flexural modulus were increased with increasing fibre content. But the strength did not increase over Vf18%. It was suggested that the strength was lowered over Vf18% in the impact test. Tensile fracture surface of SEM images are shown in Fig 8. Strength was not increased by the decrease of the interfacial bond area of the fibre and the resin because fibres pulled out from the resin were observed in Vf25% and Vf31%. In addition, the mechanical property did not improved because the localization of the fibres were observed in Vf25% and Vf31%.

Figure 5: Tensile strength and modulus of the recycled pellets

Figure 6: Flexural strength and modulus of the recycled pellets

Figure 7: Impact strength of the recycled pellets

(a)Vf5% (b)Vf12%(c)Vf18% (d)Vf25% (e)Vf31%

Figure 8: SEM image of fracture surface of the recycled pellets

Fibre length compared among various fibre content of the recycled pellets with the conventional pellets.

The result of the fibre length measurement of the recycled pellets and the conventional pellets is shown in Fig 9. Fibre length of the LFP was 6 mm. Fibre length of the recycled pellets was longer than fibre length of the SFP. Shear stress was suppressed because the screw configuration was only full flight. The result of the fibre length measurement of moulding of the recycled pellets and moulding of the conventional pellets is shown in Fig 10. The fibre breakage length of the recycled pellets was longer than the fibre breakage length of the SFP. The fibre length within the cylinder was broken by received shear stress because the recycled pellets which the pellets shape were unstable took time to metering in injection moulding. Fibres of the recycled pellets were broken because the SFP took 20 seconds to metering although the recycled pellets of Vf18% took 120 seconds to metering.

Figure 9: Fibre length between the recycled pellets, SFP and LFP

Figure 10: Fibre length between the recycled pellets moulding, SFP moulding and LFP moulding

Mechanical property of various fibre content of the recycled pellets mouldings and the conventional pellets mouldings

Fig 11, 12, 13 showed tensile property, flexural property and impact strength of the recycled pellets mouldings and the conventional pellets mouldings. Moulding of the recycled pellets of Vf18% showed nearly equal strength to the LFP of Vf18% and higher strength than the SFP of Vf18%. We were conducted SEM observation of tensile fracture surface of the recycled pellets, the SFP and the LFP. Tensile fracture surfaces are shown in Fig 14. SEM images of tensile fracture surfaces of the recycled pellets were seen breakage in the fibre comparison with the SFP and the LFP. The recycled pellets were made from the prepreg sheet which had good interfacial bonding strength because the number of vacancy which fibres were pulled out of the recycled pellets was small and the pulled out fibres was short.

Figure 11: Tensile strength and modulus of the recycled pellets, SFP and LFP

Figure 12: Flexural strength and modulus of the recycled pellets, SFP and LFP

Figure 13: Impact strength of the recycled pellets, SFP and LFP

(f)Vf18% (g)short fiber (h)long fiber

Figure 14: SEM image of fracture surface of Vf18%, SFP and LFP

Spiral flow test

The result of the spiral flow test is shown in Fig 15. Flow length of the SFP was longer than flow length of the LFP and the recycled pellets. Flow length of the LFP was shorter compared with the SFP and the recycled pellets. The reason of flow length of the LFP was short that part of flow energy of the injection moulding caused the fiber breakage in the injection process because the fibre length was left long.

Figure 15: Flow length of the recycled pellets, SFP and LFP

2.3 Hybrid injection moulding experiment and numerical analysis

2.3.1 Experimental method

Process diagram of hybrid injection moulding is shown in Fig 16. The hybrid injection moulding system is as follow. After heated insert material is pre-formed by pressmoulding, the pre-formed insert material is overmoulded by injection moulding machine. These processes are carried out in the one cycle. The moulding is shown in Fig.17. The prepreg Vf31% (Mitsubishi Rayon Co., Ltd.), the recycled pellets and SCF Vf17% were used. The injection moulding conditions are shown in Table 4. Cylinder temperature and holding pressure conditions were changed. The three-point bending test was conducted to evaluate the interfacial characteristics from experiments. Test condition of the three-point bending test showed below. The gauge length was 100 mm. The test rate was 1 mm/min. At the yield point of the first in the load-displacement curve of the three-point bending test, interfacial peeling between the injection material of the moulding and the insert material of the moulding was caused. This load of yield point was recorded as interfacial adhesion index.

Figure 16: Hybrid injection moulding process

Figure 17: Moulding made with experiment

		1	2	3	4
Screw speed	[rpm]	100			
Injection pressure	[MPa]	80			
Back pressure	[MPa]	1			
Holding pressure	[MPa]	40	80	40	80
Cylinder temperature	[°C]	220	220	260	260
Mold temperature	[°C]	40			
Injection speed	[mm/sec]	100			
Hold time	[sec]	3			
Cool down time	[sec]	10			

Table 4: Injection moulding conditions of hybrid injection moulding machine

2.3.2 Numerical analysis

Numerical simulation was carried out using LS-DYNA. Finite element analysis of a normal load on a moulding was simulated using LS-DYNA software. In this model, Terminal details of the structural shape which might not have much influence on analysis were simplified in order to shorten the analysis time. Supports and indenter of the model was assumed a rigid body. The materials assumed anisotropic elastic plastic solid and we compared the simplified analysis model result with the three-point bending test.

Fig 18. Analysis model of the three-point bending test for LS-DYNA

2.3.3 Results and discussions

The three-point bending test

Interfacial peeling between the prepreg and the injection part was observed at point of yield of load displacement curve in the result of all conditions of the three-point bending test. The load of yield point when the injection material and the insert material were peeled off by the three-point bending test is shown in Fig 19. Interfacial peeling load was improving by increasing cylinder temperature and pressure holding. The recycled pellets has a beneficial effort on the hybrid injection moulding. They also achieved excellent interfacial adhesiveness for the hybrid injection moulding between the injected material and the inserted material.

Numerical analysis

The analysis result of effective stress curve and the experimental result of load-displacement curve are shown in Fig 20. The analysis result was effective stress in side of the moulding. There was a difference in the maximum values of the displacement of the experiment and the analysis. This difference took place because analysis model was a simplified and part of the moulding of experiment were processed. From now, numerical simulation of moulding with prepreg sheet will carry out and compare with the three-point bending test.

Figure 19: The maximum load of when the injection material and the insert material were peeled off by the three-point bending test

(a) Analysis result of the three-point bending test

(b) Experimental result of the three-point bending test

Figure 20: (a) Analysis result of effective curve (b) Experimental result of load curve

4 CONCLUSION

In this study, we established recycling method to pelletize by kneading in the twin-screw extruder for the wastes of CF RTP prepreg. Furthermore, we investigated the potency of the recycled material for the hybrid injection moulding. The evaluation results of the recycled material shows below.

Screw of the twin-screw extruder was composed of all full flight.

In spite of the absence of longer fibres, recycled pellets showed excellent mechanical performance in comparison with conventional materials designing the preferable process conditions. This mechanical advantage would be due to the fact that the recycled pellets were made from the prepreg sheet which had good interfacial adhesion strength.

Strength of the recycled pellets moulding with various fibre content does not increase over Vf18%. The localization of fibres was observed in high volume fraction of fibres. The mechanical property did not improved because stress was concentrated on the localization of the fibres and the interfacial area of the fibre and the resin was decreased.

The moulding of the recycled pellets showed a high interfacial peeling load in comparison with the SFP in all conditions. They also achieved excellent interfacial adhesiveness for the hybrid injection moulding between the injected material and the inserted material.

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